

[OI] fine structure line profiles in Mon R2 and M17 SW: the puzzling nature of cold foreground material identified by [^{12}CII] self-absorption

APPENDIX

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1 Parameters of individual components

In this appendix, we list the fitted parameters for each Gaussian component for all the positions according to equation 1, 2 and 3. Tables 1 and 2 describe Mon R2 and Tables 3 to 9 describe M17 SW. Tables 10 to 13 describe the attempts of using foreground parameters of one position into another. The main components, providing more than 90% of the background and foreground material are indicated by numbers in bold print. For better visualization of the fit results, we present the fitted parameters for each of the Gaussian components for each source position in a bar plot in Figures 1 to 4.

Figure 1: The fitted components of the background emission in Mon R2 at each position observed with high S/N, both for [OI] (this paper; top) and [CII] (from the former study by Guevara et al. (2020), bottom) at different scales. The components are shown as bars with an amplitude given in column density per velocity width on an equivalent N_{HI} column density scale. The width of each bar is the FWHM width of the component. The (integrated) column density of each component is indicated by the number at the top.

Figure 2: Same as Fig. 1, but for the foreground components at the two positions observed for Mon-R2.

Figure 3: Same as Fig. 1, but for the background components fitted at the M17 SW positions.

Table 1: Mon R2 position 1 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 144.6 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	5.8E+16	7.8	2.1	3.4E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	1.8E+17	10.0	4.7	1.1E+18	
Comp. 3 [O] ₁₄₅	2.4E+16	11.7	11.0	1.4E+17	
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 77.5 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^c	3.4E+17	7.8	1.7	1.1E+19	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	3.3E+13	9.5	0.2	1.0E+15	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^c	1.1E+18	10.1	3.8	3.3E+19	
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^c	1.4E+17	11.8	9.6	4.4E+18	
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	2.3E+15	15.9	2.4	7.2E+16	
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	3.1E+15	20.7	4.1	9.6E+16	
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃	3.1E+15	23.9	7.3	9.6E+16	
T_{ex} Foreground = 19.9 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	6.5E+12	2.2	2.9	1.0E+18	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	9.5E+12	8.6	2.4	1.5E+18	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.0E+06	8.8	3.8	1.6E+11	5.9E+17
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.4E+13	11.4	1.4	2.2E+18	2.1E+17

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Table 2: Mon R2 position 2 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 227.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	2.0E+17	9.9	6.3	9.3E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	8.9E+16	11.5	2.8	4.1E+17	
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 140.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	1.8E+15	1.6	2.0	1.5E+16	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^c	9.3E+17	10.0	5.1	7.9E+18	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^c	4.1E+17	11.6	3.4	3.5E+18	
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃	1.1E+16	15.7	2.1	9.0E+16	
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	9.1E+15	17.5	3.5	7.7E+16	
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	5.6E+15	20.7	5.0	4.8E+16	
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃	2.7E+15	25.3	6.3	2.3E+16	
T_{ex} Foreground = 20.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^d	5.7E+12	7.3	1.8	8.9E+17	9E+16
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	7.0E+12	7.6	4.1	1.1E+18	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^d	2.5E+07	9.7	3.7	4.0E+12	1.4E+17
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃	1.4E+12	9.9	1.2	2.2E+17	
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃ ^d	4.4E+12	11.1	1.1	6.8E+17	2.5E+17
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃ ^d	6.5E+12	12.0	1.1	1.0E+18	1.6E+17

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Table 3: M17 SW position 0 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 200.1 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	7.0E+16	20.3	3.2	3.4E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	5.7E+16	20.7	5.2	2.8E+17	
Comp. 3 [O] ₁₄₅	1.0E+16	21.6	2.5	5.2E+16	
T_{ex} Background [O] ₆₃ = 94.9 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	3.6E+15	12.1	3.5	6.5E+16	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	2.6E+15	14.5	1.7	4.8E+16	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^c	3.4E+17	20.3	2.6	6.3E+18	
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^c	2.8E+17	20.7	4.1	5.1E+18	
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃ ^c	5.1E+16	21.5	2.0	9.4E+17	
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	1.3E+15	26.3	1.2	2.3E+16	
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃	1.0E+15	27.9	1.1	1.9E+16	
T_{ex} Foreground = 21.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^d	3.4E+10	17.0	0.1	2.9E+15	6.5E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	2.3E+12	17.4	2.1	1.9E+17	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^d	9.2E+06	19.0	3.5	7.8E+11	3.5E+17
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^d	2.0E+07	21.4	2.3	1.7E+12	7.4E+17
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	6.0E+12	21.7	1.7	5.1E+17	
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	8.2E+11	23.2	0.2	2.9E+16	
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.4E+13	24.1	0.6	1.1E+18	3.2E+17

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Table 4: M17 SW position 1 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T _{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 112.6 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	1.2E+17	18.9	4.1	8.8E+17	
T _{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 65.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	1.2E+16	12.5	3.8	6.8E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^c	8.7E+17	18.8	3.3	4.8E+19	
T _{ex} Foreground = 20.8 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^d	5.6E+12	16.4	3.3	5.3E+17	5.3E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.7E+13	18.7	3.5	1.6E+18	4.5E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.0E+13	21.3	2.3	9.8E+17	5.8E+17
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.9E+12	24.1	0.5	1.6E+17	9.1E+16

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex}.

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Table 5: M17 SW position 2 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T _{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 125.1 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	1.3E+17	19.7	4.7	8.8E+17	
T _{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 70.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	7.2E+15	12.6	3.9	3.1E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^c	8.8E+17	19.6	3.8	3.8E+19	
T _{ex} Foreground = 19.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.0E+07	14.0	3.0	2.7E+12	5.5E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	1.9E+12	16.0	3.2	5.0E+12	9.1E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^d	5.6E+10	16.7	0.5	1.5E+16	
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^d	3.0E+12	19.1	3.1	8.1E+17	3.5E+17
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃ ^d	2.5E+12	21.2	2.0	6.7E+17	5.5E+17
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃ ^d	5.2E+12	24.3	2.8	1.4E+18	6.1E+17

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex}.

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Table 6: M17 SW position 3 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 170.4 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	6.1E+16	20.0	4.6	3.3E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	3.9E+16	23.7	3.6	2.1E+17	
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 86.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	2.2E+15	9.5	3.7	5.3E+16	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	3.2E+17	20.0	3.7	7.6E+18	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃	2.1E+17	23.7	2.9	4.9E+18	
T_{ex} Foreground = 19.6 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	9.4E+11	16.9	1.6	1.5E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	1.0E+12	21.3	1.1	1.5E+17	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^d	5.6E+12	21.3	2.0	8.9E+17	5.1E+17
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^d	7.7E+12	23.7	1.5	1.2E+18	2.6E+17
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	3.6E+12	25.9	2.2	5.7E+17	

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Figure 4: Same as Fig. 3, but for the foreground components fitted at the M17 SW positions.

Table 7: M17 SW position 4 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 238.6 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	4.5E+16	20.0	2.5	2.0E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	1.9E+17	21.3	6.2	8.4E+17	
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 145.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	2.3E+16	16.5	4.0	1.8E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^c	2.0E+17	20.0	3.1	1.6E+18	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^c	8.4E+17	21.3	5.0	6.7E+18	
T_{ex} Foreground = 20.7 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.3E+07	16.6	3.0	1.3E+12	2.7E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	4.6E+07	19.6	2.1	4.6E+12	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.3E+12	19.6	1.2	1.2E+17	2.1E+17
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^d	4.6E+12	21.4	2.4	4.6E+17	3.8E+17
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	9.9E+12	21.5	0.8	9.8E+16	
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃ ^d	6.7E+12	23.8	1.1	6.5E+17	1.4E+17
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃	1.0E+13	24.6	4.1	1.0E+18	
Comp. 8 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.4E+12	26.8	3.4	1.4E+17	2.6E+17

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Table 8: M17 SW position 5 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T _{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 117.3 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	1.3E+16	13.6	4.0	8.7E+16	
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	6.3E+15	21.1	2.3	4.4E+16	
Comp. 3 [O] ₁₄₅	1.7E+16	22.9	7.3	1.2E+17	
T _{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 66.9 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^c	8.7E+16	13.6	3.2	4.3E+18	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^c	4.3E+16	21.2	1.9	2.2E+18	
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^c	1.2E+17	22.8	5.8	5.9E+18	
T _{ex} Foreground = 20.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.1E+13	12.7	2.7	1.6E+18	1.8E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.2E+12	18.4	2.0	1.8E+17	1.4E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃	3.7E+12	19.9	2.7	5.5E+17	
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃	9.0E+12	23.8	6.0	1.4E+18	
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃ ^d	1.6E+12	23.9	0.8	2.4E+17	7.2E+16

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex}.

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Table 9: M17 SW position 6 parameters.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})	N [CII] ^b (cm^{-2})
T _{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 221.6 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	9.3E+16	19.8	7.2	4.4E+17	
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	9.4E+16	21.5	2.9	4.4E+17	
T _{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 101.0 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^b	4.4E+17	19.8	5.8	6.9E+18	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^b	4.4E+17	21.5	2.3	7.0E+18	
T _{ex} Foreground = 20.2 K					
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	1.0E+13	15.5	4.0	1.4E+18	
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃ ^c	3.5E+12	17.2	3.1	4.7E+17	5.7E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^c	1.0E+12	19.1	2.2	1.4E+17	3.2E+17
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^c	2.2E+12	21.6	1.6	2.9E+17	7.6E+17
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	3.0E+08	21.6	2.3	3.9E+13	
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃ ^c	2.0E+12	24.1	0.7	2.5E+17	1.4E+17

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex}.

^b [CII] foreground column densities from Guevara et al. (2020) when the velocities match.

^c Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

^d Parameters of the components taken from the [CII] multi-component analysis from Guevara et al. (2020).

Table 10: Mon R2 position 1 parameters using free foreground parameters of position 2.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 144.6 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	5.8E+16	7.8	2.1	3.4E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	1.8E+17	10.0	4.7	1.1E+18
Comp. 3 [O] ₁₄₅	2.4E+16	11.7	11.0	1.4E+17
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 77.5 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^b	3.4E+17	7.8	1.7	1.1E+19
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	1.6E+16	9.4	1.0	5.0E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^b	1.1E+18	10.1	3.8	3.3E+19
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^b	1.4E+17	11.8	9.6	4.4E+18
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	2.3E+15	15.9	2.4	7.3E+16
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	3.1E+15	20.7	4.1	9.7E+16
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃	3.0E+15	23.9	7.3	9.5E+16
T_{ex} Foreground = 19.9 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	5.7E+12	7.3	1.8	8.9E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	7.0E+12	7.6	4.1	1.1E+18
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃	2.5E+07	9.7	3.7	4.0E+12
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃	1.4E+12	9.9	1.2	2.2E+17
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	4.4E+12	11.1	1.1	6.8E+17
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	6.5E+12	12.0	1.1	1.0E+18

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

Table 11: Mon R2 position 1 parameters using free foreground parameters of position 2.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 144.6 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	5.8E+16	7.8	2.1	3.4E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	1.8E+17	10.0	4.7	1.1E+18
Comp. 3 [O] ₁₄₅	2.4E+16	11.7	11.0	1.4E+17
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 77.5 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃ ^b	3.4E+17	7.8	1.7	1.1E+19
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	1.6E+16	9.4	1.0	5.0E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃ ^b	1.1E+18	10.1	3.8	3.3E+19
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃ ^b	1.4E+17	11.8	9.6	4.4E+18
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	2.3E+15	15.9	2.4	7.3E+16
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	3.1E+15	20.7	4.1	9.7E+16
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃	3.0E+15	23.9	7.3	9.5E+16
T_{ex} Foreground = 20.4 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	2.6E+12	7.3	1.4	3.0E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	9.3E+11	7.6	9.2	1.1E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃	2.5E+08	9.7	2.9	2.9E+13
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃	1.4E+13	9.9	2.9	1.6E+18
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	7.1E+12	11.1	0.9	8.2E+17
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	3.8E+12	12.0	0.9	4.3E+17

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

Table 12: M17 SW position 6 parameters using fixed foreground parameters of position 0.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 221.6 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	9.3E+16	19.8	7.2	4.4E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	9.4E+16	21.5	2.9	4.4E+17
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 101.0 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	4.4E+17	19.8	5.8	6.9E+18
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	4.4E+17	21.5	2.3	7.0E+18
T_{ex} Foreground = 21.0 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	5.5E+11	16.9	0.7	4.6E+16
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	1.6E+12	17.8	1.7	1.3E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃	4.6E+07	19.0	3.5	4.0E+12
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃	8.5E+07	21.4	2.3	7.2E+12
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	6.0E+12	21.7	1.7	5.1E+17
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	8.7E+11	23.2	0.2	2.8E+16
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃	1.4E+13	24.1	0.6	1.1E+18

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.

Table 13: M17 SW position 6 parameters using free foreground parameters of position 0.

Component	N_u [OI] (cm^{-2})	V (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})	N_l [OI] ^a (cm^{-2})
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₁₄₅ = 221.6 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₁₄₅	9.3E+16	19.8	7.2	4.4E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₁₄₅	9.4E+16	21.5	2.9	4.4E+17
T_{ex} Background [OI] ₆₃ = 101.0 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	4.4E+17	19.8	5.8	6.9E+18
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	4.4E+17	21.5	2.3	7.0E+18
T_{ex} Foreground = 20.0 K				
Comp. 1 [O] ₆₃	5.5E+12	16.9	3.1	8.1E+17
Comp. 2 [O] ₆₃	5.0E+12	17.8	6.8	7.3E+17
Comp. 3 [O] ₆₃	4.6E+06	19.0	35.0	6.8E+11
Comp. 4 [O] ₆₃	8.5E+06	21.4	22.5	1.2E+12
Comp. 5 [O] ₆₃	1.3E+12	21.7	1.3	1.8E+17
Comp. 6 [O] ₆₃	8.7E+10	23.2	0.2	2.7E+15
Comp. 7 [O] ₆₃	1.7E+12	24.1	0.7	2.4E+17

^a Column density of the lower level population of the transition, calculated from N_u [OI] and T_{ex} .

^b Components derived from the [OI] 145 μm Gaussian fitting.